

Editorial**Non-Communicable Diseases: The Ticking Time Bomb**

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Pakistan is under a silent but rapidly increasing health crisis. Because of the recent pandemic in particular, infectious diseases continue to grab significant attention and compared to non-communicable diseases (NCDs)—such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, cancer, and chronic respiratory illnesses—have become the leading cause of mortality rate, accounting for over 60% of all annual deaths in the country¹.

One of the most frightening facts is the dramatic rise in diabetes cases, which has increased from 6.3 million cases in 2011 to nearly 36 million adults in 2024, making Pakistan one of the most vulnerable countries worldwide in terms of diabetes mellitus prevalence¹. Sadly, diabetes alone causes more than 1,100 deaths daily. On the other hand, cardiovascular diseases now account for more than half of NCD-related deaths, causing around 450,000 annual fatalities¹.

This drastic upward trend in NCDs can result from a joint effort of sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy food, environmental factors, and a lack of health awareness². The prevalence of Obesity has also increased globally, with 40% of the population being overweight or obese, and the adult obesity rate estimated at 28% (WHO, 2024). The exacerbation of chronic respiratory conditions is due to Environmental factors, such as poor air quality in cities like Lahore and Karachi, which further exacerbate the burden of chronic respiratory conditions³.

The concern is that healthcare agencies have turned a blind eye to preventive measures within Pakistan. Ideally, primordial and primary preventative measures such as early detection and timely treatment should be the key components of a healthcare system; however, sadly both measures remain limited or inaccessible, especially in rural areas⁴. Subsequently, patients are not timely diagnosed and the annual mortality level significantly increases with every passing year.

To Combat this ticking time bomb, a nationwide mass screening program must be initiated with low or free-of-cost basic health testing (blood sugar, blood pressure, cholesterol, and cancer markers)⁴. Moreover, some parallel projects like health education campaigns, are integrated into school curricula and community outreach, in order to raise awareness in communities².

Finally, as processed food consumption plays a crucial role in this context, the regulation of processed foods is inevitable. Pakistan should adopt Front-of-Pack Warning Labels (FOPWL) for sugar-rich and high-fat food products, similar to models used successfully in Latin America⁵. In megacities health educational programs should promote walking, physical activity, and green spaces to reduce sedentary behavior.

Pakistan has reached the highest point and from here the only way out is to take coordinated and urgent actions to overcome the seriously falling standards of its healthcare system and to overcome the crisis of NCDs. Ignoring this reality can overwhelm the healthcare system and paralyze economic productivity—a timely reminder to all the concerned authorities before the epidemic becomes an irreversible national tragedy.

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